

Research Article

Laplace and Inverse Laplace Transform Techniques in Cryptography Using the Series $t \sinh rt$

N. Mohana*¹, A. Angel kulanthai theresa²

¹ Assistant professor of Mathematics, PG & Research Department of Mathematics, A.V.C. College (Autonomous).

² PG Scholar, PG & Research Department of Mathematics, A.V.C. College (Autonomous)

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 03 May 2026

Keywords:

Cryptography, Laplace Transform, Hyperbolic Functions, Modular Arithmetic, Secure Communication.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.19985681

ABSTRACT

Cryptography plays a vital role in securing information in modern digital communication systems. With the rapid expansion of electronic transactions and online services, ensuring secure data transmission has become increasingly essential. This paper proposes a novel mathematical approach to cryptography based on the Laplace Transform. In the proposed method, plaintext is converted into a numerical or functional representation and encrypted using the Laplace Transform, generating a transformed ciphertext. The original message is retrieved by applying the corresponding Inverse Laplace Transform. The use of mathematical transformation introduces additional computational complexity, thereby enhancing resistance against unauthorized access and attacks. The results indicate that the proposed technique improves data security while maintaining computational efficiency and flexibility. This approach demonstrates the potential of mathematical transforms in designing secure cryptographic systems. Potential applications include banking security, password protection, secure data transmission, and one-time password (OTP) systems.

INTRODUCTION

Information security is a fundamental requirement in modern digital communication systems, driven by the rapid growth of online transactions, cloud computing, and data exchange technologies. Ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and authenticity of information has become increasingly important. Cryptography addresses

these challenges by transforming plaintext into ciphertext using mathematically reliable techniques¹.

Traditional cryptographic methods are primarily based on modular arithmetic, substitution, and permutation operations. In recent years, there has been growing interest in exploring advanced mathematical tools to develop more secure and

*Corresponding Author: N. Mohana

Address: Assistant professor of Mathematics, PG & Research Department of Mathematics, A.V.C. College (Autonomous)

Email : mohanagopikrishnan@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

efficient encryption schemes. In this context, mathematical transformations offer a structured and systematic framework for data encoding and decoding². This creates a demand for innovative approaches to strengthen data security in modern communication systems.

In this paper, we present a cryptographic technique based on the Laplace Transform and its inverse. The proposed method represents plaintext as coefficients of a function involving the series $t \sinh rt$, and applies the transform to generate encrypted data. The original message is accurately recovered using the corresponding Inverse Laplace Transform along with key values.

The proposed approach combines mathematical transformation and modular arithmetic to provide a systematic and mathematically rigorous framework for secure communication. It offers enhanced security through increased computational complexity while maintaining efficiency in implementation. Potential applications include digital communication networks, password protection, secure data transmission, and banking systems.

This approach provides a novel mathematical framework for encryption using Laplace Transform techniques³. It introduces an additional layer of complexity, making unauthorized decoding more difficult, and is flexible enough to be adapted to different types of data representations. Accurate recovery of the original message is ensured through the corresponding Inverse Laplace Transform. Overall, the method demonstrates effectiveness and reliability for secure communication systems.

2. PRELIMINARIES

Definition 2.1

Plaintext refers to the original readable message that can be understood without any transformation.

Definition 2.2

When a plaintext message is encoded using an appropriate encryption scheme, the resulting message is called ciphertext.

Definition 2.3

Encryption is the process of converting a readable message (plaintext) into an encoded form (ciphertext), whereas decryption is the reverse process that restores the ciphertext back to its original plaintext form. Both encryption and decryption rely on two fundamental elements: a well-defined algorithm and a corresponding key. The key plays a crucial role in controlling the transformation process, thereby ensuring the security of the communication.

Definition 2.4

In cryptography, modular arithmetic is used to convert numerical values into letters.

For an integer a ,

$$a \equiv r \pmod{26}$$

where r is the remainder when a is divided by 26.

2.1. The Laplace Transform:

If $f(t)$ is a function defined for all positive values of t , then the Laplace transform of $f(t)$ is defined as

$$L\{f(t)\} = F(s) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-st} f(t) dt$$

provided that the integral exists. Here the parameter s is a real or complex number.

The corresponding Inverse Laplace transform is

$$L^{-1}\{F(s)\} = f(t)$$

2.2. Linear Property

Laplace transform is a linear transform.

That is, if

$$L\{f_1(t)\} = F_1(s), L\{f_2(t)\} = F_2(s), \dots, L\{f_n(t)\} = F_n(s)$$

Then

$$L\{c_1f_1(t) + c_2f_2(t) + \dots + c_nf_n(t)\} = c_1F_1(s) + c_2F_2(s) + \dots + c_nF_n(s)$$

where c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n are constants.

2.3. Standard Results on Laplace Transform

Laplace Transform has diverse applications in fields such as mechanics, electrical circuits, beam analysis, heat conduction, wave propagation, transmission lines, signals and systems, control engineering, communication systems, hydrodynamics, and solar studies.

It is widely employed for solving differential equations, analysing systems, and developing mathematical models. Moreover, it plays a role in cryptography by supporting encryption, decryption, and secure data transformation. Hence, it stands as a fundamental tool in both engineering applications and information security.

Here we consider the following standard results of Laplace transform

$$1. L\{\sinh kt\} = \frac{k}{s^2 - k^2}, \quad s \geq |k|$$

$$L^{-1}\left\{\frac{k}{s^2 - k^2}\right\} = \sinh kt$$

$$2. L\{t^n\} = \frac{n!}{s^{n+1}}, \quad n \in N$$

$$L^{-1}\left\{\frac{n!}{s^{n+1}}\right\} = t^n, \quad n \in N$$

$$3. L\{t^n f(t)\} = \left(\frac{-d}{ds}\right)^n F(s)$$

$$L^{-1}\left\{\left(\frac{-d}{ds}\right)^n F(s)\right\} = t^n f(t)$$

$$4. L\{t^n e^{kt}\} = \frac{n!}{(s - k)^{n+1}}$$

$$L^{-1}\left\{\frac{n!}{(s - k)^{n+1}}\right\} = t^n e^{kt}$$

where $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ are positive integers.

3. MAIN RESULTS

3.1 Method of Encryption

We consider standard expansion

$$\begin{aligned} \sinh rt &= rt + \frac{r^3 t^3}{3!} + \frac{r^5 t^5}{5!} + \dots + \frac{r^{2i+1} t^{2i+1}}{(2i+1)!} + \dots \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{(rt)^{2i+1}}{(2i+1)!} \\ t \sinh rt &= rt^2 + \frac{r^3 t^4}{3!} + \frac{r^5 t^6}{5!} + \frac{r^7 t^8}{7!} + \dots + \dots \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{r^{2i+1} t^{2i+2}}{(2i+1)!} \end{aligned}$$

where $r \in N$ is a constant with N is the set of natural numbers.

Step 1

Select the message to be sent that is plaintext.

Step 2

The plaintext can be organized as a finite sequence of numbers as allocate 0 to A and 1 to B and so on Z will be 25.

Step 3

Our plaintext is **CIRCLE**

By above step our plaintext is equivalent to 2, 8, 17, 2, 11, 4.

Step 4

Write the numbers as coefficients of G_i , Therefore our plaintext is

$$G_0 = 2, G_1 = 8, G_2 = 17, G_3 = 2, G_4 = 11, G_5 = 4,$$

$$G_n = 0 \text{ for } n \geq 6$$

Step 5

Write these numbers as the coefficient in $t \sinh rt$ where r is a constant.

Let us consider

$$\begin{aligned} f(t) &= Gt \sinh 2t \\ f(t) &= t \left\{ G_0 \cdot 2t + G_1 \frac{2^3 t^3}{3!} + G_2 \frac{2^5 t^5}{5!} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + G_3 \frac{2^7 t^7}{7!} + G_4 \frac{2^9 t^9}{9!} + G_5 \frac{2^{11} t^{11}}{11!} \right\} \\ &= G_0 \frac{2t^2}{1!} + G_1 \frac{2^3 t^4}{3!} + G_2 \frac{2^5 t^6}{5!} \\ &\quad + G_3 \frac{2^7 t^8}{7!} + G_4 \frac{2^9 t^{10}}{9!} + G_5 \frac{2^{11} t^{12}}{11!} \\ f(t) &= 2 \frac{2t^2}{1!} + 8 \frac{2^3 t^4}{3!} + 17 \frac{2^5 t^6}{5!} \\ &\quad + 2 \frac{2^7 t^8}{7!} + 11 \frac{2^9 t^{10}}{9!} + 4 \frac{2^{11} t^{12}}{11!} \end{aligned}$$

Step 6

Taking Laplace transform on both sides

$$L\{f(t)\} = L\{Gt \sinh 2t\}$$

$$= L \left\{ 2 \frac{2t^2}{1!} + 8 \frac{2^3 t^4}{3!} + 17 \frac{2^5 t^6}{5!} + 2 \frac{2^7 t^8}{7!} + 11 \frac{2^9 t^{10}}{9!} + 4 \frac{2^{11} t^{12}}{11!} \right\}$$

$$\therefore L\{t^n\} = \frac{n!}{s^{n+1}}$$

Applying Laplace Transform each term separately,

$$L \left\{ 2 \cdot \frac{2t^2}{1!} \right\} = 2 \times \frac{2}{1!} \times \frac{2}{s^3}$$

$$L \left\{ 2 \cdot \frac{2t^2}{1!} \right\} = \frac{8}{s^3}$$

Similarly,

$$L \left\{ 8 \cdot \frac{2^3 t^4}{3!} \right\} = \frac{256}{s^5}$$

$$L \left\{ 17 \cdot \frac{2^5 t^6}{5!} \right\} = \frac{3264}{s^7}$$

$$L \left\{ 2 \cdot \frac{2^7 t^8}{7!} \right\} = \frac{2048}{s^9}$$

$$L \left\{ 11 \cdot \frac{2^9 t^{10}}{9!} \right\} = \frac{56320}{s^{11}}$$

$$L \left\{ 4 \cdot \frac{2^{11} t^{12}}{11!} \right\} = \frac{98304}{s^{13}}$$

\therefore We get,

$$L\{f(t)\} = \frac{8}{s^3} + \frac{256}{s^5} + \frac{3264}{s^7} + \frac{2048}{s^9} + \frac{56320}{s^{11}} + \frac{98304}{s^{13}}$$

Step 7

Therefore resultant values are
8 256 3264 2048 56320 98304

The resultant values are reduced using modulo 26

That is,

$$\begin{aligned} 8 &= 8 \text{ mod } 26 &= 8 \\ 256 &= 256 \text{ mod } 26 &= 22 \\ 2048 &= 2048 \text{ mod } 26 &= 20 \\ 3264 &= 3264 \text{ mod } 26 &= 14 \\ 56320 &= 56320 \text{ mod } 26 &= 20 \\ 98304 &= 98304 \text{ mod } 26 &= 24 \end{aligned}$$

Hence we get our ciphertext as **I W O U E Y** which is equivalent to 8 22 14 20 4 24

with key k_i for $i = 0,1,2, \dots$

Step 8

To find the key values,

Let Original value be K_i and Remainder be r_i

Then,

$$\text{Key} = \frac{K_i - r_i}{26}$$

$$\begin{aligned} K_i = 8, \quad r_i = 8 &\Rightarrow \frac{8 - 8}{26} \\ &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} K_i = 256, \quad r_i = 22 &\Rightarrow \frac{256 - 22}{26} \\ &= 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} K_i = 3264, \quad r_i = 14 &\Rightarrow \frac{3264 - 14}{26} \\ &= 125 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we can find key values for remaining.

Therefore, the key values are 0, 9, 125, 78, 2166, 3780.

Hence the message **C I R C L E** is encrypted as **I W O U E Y** with key is 0, 9, 125, 78, 2166, 3780.

Theorem 3.1

The given plaintext in terms of $G_i, i = 1,2,3 \dots$, under Laplace Transform of $Gt \sinh rt$ (that is by writing them as a coefficient of $t \sinh rt$, and then taking Laplace Transform)

can be converted to ciphertext G'_i , where

$$G'_i = q_i - 26k_i, \text{ for } i = 0,1,2,3, \dots$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} q_i &= r^{2i+1}(2i + 2)G_i \text{ for } i \\ &= 0,1,2, \dots \end{aligned}$$

$$r = 1,2,3, \dots$$

with

$$\frac{K_i - r_i}{26}$$

key,

3.2 Method of Decryption

Received ciphertext is **I W O U E Y** with keys 0 9 125 78 2166 3780

Step 1

The ciphertext can be organized as a finite sequence of numbers as allocate 0 to A and 1 to B and so on Z will be 25.

Step 2

The ciphertext **IWOUEY** is equivalent to 8 22 14 20 4 24

Step 3

Write the numbers as coefficients of G'_i ,

$$\begin{aligned} G'_0 &= 8, G'_1 = 22, G'_2 = 14, G'_3 = 20, G'_4 \\ &= 4, G'_5 = 24, G'_n = 0 \text{ for } n \geq 6 \end{aligned}$$

Step 4

Add the corresponding key values to obtain q_i

From theorem,

$$q_i = G'_i + 26k_i, \quad k_i \text{ for } i = 0, 1, 2 \dots \text{ as } 0, 9, 125, 78, 2166, 3780$$

$$q_0 = G'_0 + 26k_0 = 8 + 26(0) = 8$$

$$q_1 = G'_1 + 26k_1 = 22 + 26(9) = 256$$

$$q_2 = G'_2 + 26k_2 = 14 + 26(125) = 3264$$

$$q_3 = G'_3 + 26k_3 = 20 + 26(78) = 2048$$

$$q_4 = G'_4 + 26k_4 = 4 + 26(2166) = 56320$$

$$q_5 = G'_5 + 26k_5 = 24 + 26(3780) = 98304$$

Step 5

Form the transformed expression using q_i ,

$$G\left\{-\frac{d}{ds}\right\}\left(\frac{2}{s^2 - 2^2}\right) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{q_i}{s^{2i+3}}$$

$$= \frac{8}{s^3} + \frac{256}{s^5} + \frac{3264}{s^7} + \frac{2048}{s^9} + \frac{56320}{s^{11}} + \frac{98304}{s^{13}}$$

Step 6

Apply Inverse Laplace Transform to the expression.

$$= L^{-1}\left\{\frac{8}{s^3} + \frac{256}{s^5} + \frac{3264}{s^7} + \frac{2048}{s^9} + \frac{56320}{s^{11}} + \frac{98304}{s^{13}}\right\}$$

Step 7

Apply Inverse Laplace Transform

$$L^{-1}\left\{\frac{1}{s^{n+1}}\right\} = \frac{t^n}{n!}$$

We know that,

$$f(t) = G_0 \frac{2t^2}{1!} + G_1 \frac{2^3 t^4}{3!} + G_2 \frac{2^5 t^6}{5!} + G_3 \frac{2^7 t^8}{8!} + G_4 \frac{2^9 t^{10}}{10!} + G_5 \frac{2^{11} t^{12}}{11!}$$

Taking Inverse Laplace Transform on each term separately

$$L^{-1}\left\{\frac{8}{s^3}\right\} = 8 \times \frac{t^2}{2!}$$

To obtain the original coefficients G_i

Let C be integer coefficient

$$C \times \frac{2}{1!} = 8 \times \frac{t^2}{2!}$$

$$C = 8 \times \frac{t^2}{2 \times 1} \times \frac{1}{2}$$

$$C = 2t^2$$

$$L^{-1}\left\{\frac{8}{s^3}\right\} = 2t^2$$

Similarly, we obtain

$$L^{-1}\left\{\frac{256}{s^5}\right\} = 8t^4$$

$$L^{-1}\left\{\frac{3264}{s^7}\right\} = 17t^6$$

$$L^{-1}\left\{\frac{2048}{s^9}\right\} = 2t^8$$

$$L^{-1}\left\{\frac{56320}{s^{11}}\right\} = 11t^{10}$$

$$L^{-1}\left\{\frac{98304}{s^{13}}\right\} = 4t^{12}$$

Step 8

Substituting these coefficients in $f(t)$ we get
 $f(t) = Gt \sinh 2t$

$$f(t) = 2 \frac{2t^2}{1!} + 8 \frac{2^3t^4}{3!} + 17 \frac{2^5t^6}{5!} + 2 \frac{2^7t^8}{8!} + 11 \frac{2^9t^{10}}{10!} + 4 \frac{2^{11}t^{12}}{11!}$$

$$f(t) = G_i t^j \sinh rt, \quad \text{where } r, j \in N$$

Step 9

Convert the coefficient back to letters

That is, 2 8 17 2 11 4 is equivalent to **CIRCLE**

Hence the ciphertext **IWOUEY** is decrypted as the plaintext **CIRCLE** with key 0, 9,

125, 78, 2166, 3780.

Theorem 3.2

The given ciphertext string in terms of $G_i, i = 1,2,3 \dots$ with the given key k_i for

$i = 0,1,2, \dots$, under Inverse Laplace transform of

$$G \left\{ -\frac{d}{ds} \right\} \left(\frac{2}{s^2 - 2^2} \right) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{q_i}{s^{2i+3}}$$

can be converted to plaintext G_i , where

$$G_i = \frac{26k_i + G'_i}{r^{2i+1}(2i + 2)}, \quad i = 0,1,2, \dots$$

and

$$q_i = 26k_i + G'_i, \quad \text{for } i = 0,1,2, \dots$$

4. GENERALIZATION

We now extend the results obtained in section 3 for more generalized functions. Let N be the set of natural numbers. For encryption of the given message string in terms of G_i . We consider the function

Following the same procedure discussed in section 3, we take the Laplace transform of $f(t)$. Then the given message string G_i can be converted into the ciphertext G'_i , where

$$G'_i = G_i r^{2i+1} (2i + 2)(2i + 3) \dots (2i + j + 1) \pmod{26}$$

Let

$$q_i = G_i r^{2i+1} (2i + 2)(2i + 3) \dots (2i + j + 1), \quad i = 0,1,2,3 \dots$$

and the key is defined by

$$k_i = \frac{q_i - G'_i}{26} \quad \text{for } i = 0,1,2 \dots$$

Theorem 4.1

The given plaintext string in terms of $G_i, i = 1,2,3 \dots$ under the Laplace transform of $Gt^j \sinh rt$ (that is, by writing them as coefficients of $t^j \sinh rt$ and then taking the Laplace transform) can be converted into ciphertext G'_i , where

$$G'_i = q_i - 26k_i, \quad \text{for } i = 0,1,2,3, \dots$$

and

$$q_i = G_i r^{2i+1} (2i + 2)(2i + 3) \dots (2i + j + 1)$$

with key

$$k_i = \frac{q_i - G'_i}{26} \quad \text{for } i = 0,1,2, \dots$$

Theorem 4.2

The given ciphertext string in terms of G'_i , $i = 1,2,3 \dots$ with key k_i , for $i = 0,1,2, \dots$ under the Inverse Laplace transform of

$$G \left\{ \left(-\frac{d}{ds} \right)^j \frac{r}{(s^2 - r^2)} \right\} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{q_i}{s^{2i+j+2}}, \quad i = 0,1,2 \dots$$

can be converted back into the plaintext G_i , where

$$G_i = \frac{26k_i + G'_i}{r^{2i+1}(2i+2)(2i+3) \dots (2i+j+1)}, \quad i = 0,1,2 \dots$$

and

$$q_i = 26k_i + G'_i, \quad \text{for } i = 0,1,2, \dots$$

4.1 Encryption algorithm

i. Treat every letter in the plaintext message as a number, so that using the mapping

$$A = 0, B = 1, C = 2, \dots, Z = 25.$$

ii. The plaintext message G_i is organized as a finite sequence of numbers based on the above conversion. Only consider G_i till the length of input string, ie., $i = 0$ to $n - 1$

iii. Consider a suitable function $f(t)$. Take Laplace transform and obtain the required formula for encryption. Hence each character in the input string converts to a new position G'_i .

iv. Key value for each character can be obtained from the corresponding relation

v. Send G'_i and k_i as pair to the receiver.

4.2 Decryption algorithm

i. The receiver obtains the encrypted pair G'_i and k_i .

ii. Use the key values to recover the original numerical sequence corresponding to the plaintext message.

iii. Arrange the obtained numbers as a finite sequence.

iv. Convert each number of the sequence into the corresponding alphabet using the mapping $A = 0, B = 1, C = 2, \dots, Z = 25$.

v. The resulting string obtained is the original plaintext message.

5. ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLES

Suppose the original message be string 'CIRCLE'. Using the results of section 4, we can convert it to

1. 'MEMOOA' for $r = 1, j = 2$
2. 'SKEGIA' for $r = 2, j = 3$
3. 'SMCSAA' for $r = 3, j = 4$
4. 'QUGMUM' for $r = 4, j = 1$
5. 'YOOEAA' for $r = 5, j = 5$

6. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a novel cryptographic technique based on the Laplace Transform and its inverse for secure data communication. The method converts plaintext into an encrypted mathematical form and accurately reconstructs the original message through the inverse process. By combining mathematical transformations with modular arithmetic, the approach ensures a structured and reliable encryption framework. The use of series representation enhances the complexity and strength of the system. The proposed technique is suitable for applications such as secure messaging, banking security, and digital data protection. Furthermore, it offers a

promising direction for developing advanced mathematical models in cryptography.

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors express their sincere gratitude to the PG & Research Department of Mathematics,

A. V. C. College (Autonomous), for their support and encouragement in completing this work.

REFERENCES

1. Hiwarekar AP: A new method of cryptography using Laplace transform. International Journal of Mathematical Archive. 2012;3(3):1193–1197.
2. Hiwarekar AP: A new method of cryptography using Laplace transform of hyperbolic functions. International Journal of Mathematical Archive. 2013;4(2):208–213.
3. Hiwarekar AP: New mathematical modeling for cryptography. Journal of Information Assurance and Security, MIR Lab USA. 2014;9:27–33.
4. Hiwarekar AP: Application of Laplace Transform for Cryptographic Scheme, proceeding of World Congress on Engineering Vol. II, LNCS, 95-100, (2013).
5. Eric C, Ronald K, James WC: Network Security Bible. 2nd ed. Wiley India; 2009.
6. Sukalyan Som and Moumita Som: DNA secret writing with Laplace Transform. International Journal of Computer Applications 50(5):44-50, (July 2012).
7. Naga Lakshmi G, Ravi Kumar B and Chandra Sekhar A: A cryptographic scheme of Laplace transforms, International Journal of Mathematical Archive-2, 2515-2519, (2011).
8. Johannes A. Buchmann: Introduction to Cryptography, 4th edition, Indian Reprint, Springer,(2009).
9. Stallings W: Cryptography and network security, 4th edition, Prentice Hall, (2005).
10. Swati D, Archana AS, Swati J: Laplace transformation based cryptographic technique in network security. International Journal of Computer Applications. 2016;136(7).
11. Stallings W: Network security essentials: Applications and standards, first edition, Pearson Education, Asia, (2001).
12. Dhanorkar GA, Hiwarekar AP. A generalized Hill cipher using matrix transformation. International Journal of Mathematical Sciences and Engineering Applications. 2011;5(IV):19–23.
13. Overbey J, Traves W, Wojdylo J: On the Keyspace of the Hill Cipher, Cryptologia. 29, 59-72, January 2005.
14. Barr TH: Invitation to Cryptography, Prentice Hall, (2002).

HOW TO CITE: N. Mohana*, A. Angel kulanthai theresa, Laplace and Inverse Laplace Transform Techniques in Cryptography Using the Series $t \sinh rt$, Int. J. in Engi. Sci., 2026, Vol 3, Issue 5, 8-16. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19985681>

